

Some Basics on (mainly qualitative) Research Design

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To allow some better grasp of what is meant by qualitative research design, I have enclosed a general description of the very start: how to get a question. I hasten to add that there is no one description acceptable to all. The following is meant to provide one way among many.

The following spends lots of time on theorising. This can lead to a misunderstanding. My intention is not to force people to become all theorists in the usual style of believing that one's own research is the best kind of research there is. Almost to the contrary, the intention is to take some of the debilitating awe away from 'theory', which seems reduced to some form of 'grand conceptual discussion' or 'profound thinking', where Aristotle meets International Relations, and nothing less. There are more mundane ways of theorising, and, by implication, many people theorise without knowing, yet can use these ways to justify their research and findings.

Finally, the following speaks more to the more usual designs in IR, thereby mentioning but discussing less normative designs and ethnographic designs. This should not imply any less relevance of such designs.

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As a general rule, any research design should address three basic questions:

- *what* is my central question / puzzle / dilemma or paradox?
- *why* should anybody (who?) care? (what makes it significant? For whom?)
- *how* am I going to answer the question or resolve the puzzle / dilemma or paradox?

These three aspects are connected. The central question (what) needs to be significant (*why*). And for this, it is good to think in terms of the unexpected event or irregularity, the theoretical paradox or the moral dilemma (depending on whether your thesis has an empirical, theoretical or normative aim). Once you know what you wish to contribute and to whom that should speak, you also have a better sense of which theory, methodology, and then which methods are needed (the *how*). I.e. in the just presented setup, the choice of methods is dependent on the question (problem-driven design), not primary (method-driven design). Obviously, certain theoretical affinities will tend to go for certain questions, which will then tend to be followed by certain methods. Someone who is interested in macro-events and large general claims based on regularity, will tend to have questions which, in turn, will most likely look for a positivist design and quantitative methods. Someone who wishes to understand how it became possible for a certain government to embark on a certain foreign policy, will tend to go for qualitative and often interpretivist methods (the two are not the same, though). But it is truly helpful to ensure significance by letting one driven by problems, not methods (except if the problem is itself a methodological one).

In the following, I will mainly present some ideas about the first two questions, which have to do with the beginning of a thesis (which can take years!) in which one comes to define the question, its audience and significance. I will not touch the actual methods, which would take far too much.

1. The purpose of research: communicating relevant knowledge

Any research has a purpose (beyond getting a degree and killing time). This truism has many important implications.

First, it speaks to someone, it has an audience. Research is not an exercise in self-inflicted boredom but wants to communicate something. Be sure for whom and to whom you want to talk with your research. This can be the perennial world of ideas; and you communicate with Plato and Kant. It can be the particular scientific or political community of yours. In sum, you tell someone else a story, he or she should not miss.

Second, this communication has to do with knowledge. In principle, research should contribute to ‘our’ knowledge (here represented by the audience of the research). Whether or not this is part of ‘accumulating knowledge’ is a hot debate for the philosophers of science; but it changes little to the basic fact that research aims at uncovering something formerly unknown or neglected.

Third, not everything unknown or neglected is worth being dug up. Many of the secrets of human life are not worth exploring. Well, sure, but who says what is and what is not? Any audience has informal or open criteria for judging the relevance of a communication. Being witty can be such a criterion for cocktail parties. In the academic environment of social and political science/international relations, there are others (although a sense of humour does never harm). This includes political relevance, but that is usually not enough: it needs to contribute to our existing knowledge as it is stored in our existing theories. And explanations

ultimately rely on theories. Therefore, theories are so crucial. They are not just a mark of distinction for the alleged insider; they provide the backdrop against which we justify the finding of relevant knowledge that feeds into them. Theorising is not a single exercise, though (see below).

Summing up: Social sciences look at the real world by asking questions about the latter. Hence, it is not enough to have simply a topic in mind, a broad field; rather, one should think in terms of specific questions. These questions help to unravel the formerly unknown or the unexpected, the paradoxes and dilemmas, whose relevance usually derives from, and is embedded in, a debate in historical, political, philosophical and/or moral terms.

2. The ‘puzzle’: explaining/understanding the unexpected

In general, research should be designed to address and explain/understand something which is unexpected, something which warrants an investigation and then a communication by which one addresses the audience with the findings. Put shortly: it requires a ‘puzzle’, which is of a valid concern for the audience, whether or not the audience already knows that. Ask yourself, what is the unexpected issue, either empirical or theoretical, that you would like to answer. There must be something which has spurred your curiosity. Try to put it into a question, possibly a ‘why?’, a ‘how possible?’, or a ‘how ought?’ question. Although such questions are not necessary for all theses, thinking in these terms leads you away from purely descriptive theses.

It is however necessary that you find something either in the theoretical discussion or in the relation between theory and the empirical world, which does not fit: it needs explanation. The idea of explaining something unexpected implies the idea of a yardstick which defines what is expected. Usually such yardsticks are derived from assumptions which, in turn, are held together within theories. The more reflective research is about its assumptions and how they fit together, the better.

There is one exception to this rule. There is one criterion of relevance which is not derived from the ‘unexpected’ but from the inherent importance of the issue itself.

Example: Is it possible that nuclear weapons can go off unintended?

Be careful that not all type of answers to this question will concern the political scientist. If the research is conducted in purely technical terms, trying to find out whether the weapons were engineered such as to avoid involuntary detonation, then the research is not in the social, but the natural sciences – whatever its political importance. Only if the research is conducted upon the political component of making a nuclear device explode, is it a question of political science. Usually, this is handled with bureaucratic decision-making models which provide policy recommendations of how to limit the risk (‘Dr. Strangelove’).

Drawback: there are few questions which have this overriding importance. Moreover, some of the answers can quickly slide into some kind of technical description and little analytical work. Good for a short policy paper, this can be risky for a thesis. Hence, it usually pays to think about puzzles within their respective audiences.

3. Types of puzzles: empirical and theoretical

There are two types of theses, depending on their puzzle and hence ultimate aim. It is the aim, which defines whether a thesis is fundamentally empirical or theoretical. In the two clean

ideal types, you either use empirics to establish a theoretical contribution, or you use theories to make an empirical contribution. In other words, one cannot avoid theory. This is obvious where the final aim is a contribution to existing theoretical knowledge. But it also applies to theses which ultimately want to illuminate an empirical issue (event, policy, etc.). Even if your puzzle is empirical, you need theories to oppose conflicting interpretations and to see the assumptions on the basis of which they could have been made. Although your curiosity is about understanding that particular event, theories might help you to sort out, distinguish and compare the different interpretations. The discussion will oppose theories as a means for making an empirical point.

Let me use the example of the understanding of the End of the Cold War for distinguishing an empirical from a theoretical purpose, even if both research designs mix theory and empirical analysis. An empirical thesis would want to understand why the USSR collapsed, for instance. For this, it will rely on different theoretically informed hypothesis, but the aim and conclusion of the paper will be about the best explanation of this empirical event. The thesis's strength derives both from the logical articulation of the different interpretations and the empirical data for which it proposes a better fit. Inversely, some might be interested to see what the collapse of the USSR tells us about the relative explanatory power of different theories. Although the argument relies on an empirical case, the aim and conclusion of the paper will assess different theories. Indeed, often (better) theses try to combine the two approaches to some extent: for all its risks of mixing the two designs (see below), it can add relevance.

Yet, it is almost always preferable to have a clear hierarchy or sequence of these two contributions in order to keep a clean design. Since the two are mixed, it may seem not really important to decide whether the thesis is mainly empirical or theoretical. But it does make an important difference for drafting the thesis. In a traditional setup, the first chapter after the intro refers to that type of knowledge *to* which the thesis is mainly contributing. If it is a thesis that aims at theory development, then the state of the art of that theoretical discussion, and its lacunae, come here. You will be assessed by how well you master that state of the art and how significant the contribution is – both within the theoretical debate you refer to and outside of it. Inversely, if your main contribution is empirical, this chapter will assess the state of the art of the empirical discussion of your topic. Again, you will be judged by how well you master the debate and whether your contribution is significant. In both cases, you may aim for an internal critique, which implies that you accept the terms of the analysis but show that it can lead to other results, and/or an external critique, by which you show that the same or similar results could be reached through another path. Internal critiques are a fairer starting point, but they need not be the end.

Besides engaging the literature *to* which you make your contribution, there can be, however, another field of literature *with* which you wish to make that contribution. It is possible, but not necessary, that the two are the same. If the literature *with* which you will make your analysis is different from your main audience, then it will follow in a separate chapter. For this reason, being clear about the sequence of the contributions is crucial, since that will affect the content of these two chapters and the very logic of your argument.

Also, the expectation about the two literatures will be different. You must show to make a contribution *to* some state of the art. Here, some 'value added' is expected. If, for doing this, you use some other literature, that usage is instrumental and does not require innovation

of any sorts, only accuracy. In his famous *Essence of Decision*, Graham T. Allison speaks to the IR literature in Foreign Policy Analysis, while mobilising e.g. organisational and psychological theories for developing his models. The research will be judged for the contribution to FPA not to psychological theory, which was just a means in this endeavour, although one will need to show to have used it accurately.

One classical problem for writing theses is that one may find oneself not able to make any contribution well. This is not very good, but quite common (and people still end up delivering it). The temptation is then great to shift back and forth between theory and empirics (or two types of literatures). For instance, you have a hunch that shifting the analytical lens will contribute to a better understanding of the empirics; but then the empirical evidence is not really doing it or is turning out to be trivial. You may then wish to invert the logic and use the empirics for making a theoretical point; but often that overburdens the theoretical uptake of the empirical findings and can hence not be used to yield such a contribution. Not deciding where the contribution lies may not only end up muddling the logic of the thesis, and potentially ending by making none. In short, it is quite crucial to be clear about the target audience to which you make a contribution, even if your research carries less of a value added than you had initially envisaged.

Addendum: As the above discussion shows, most research designs have at least an implicit comparative component. It establishes relevance. One way of controlling that your particular event is justifiably significant is to make sure that your case is telling a story beyond itself, so that people who are not specialists on your topic, might find it interesting to know about it. One way consists in presenting possible comparable cases or events. If your case is similar to others, and this is widely acknowledged, there is not much of a puzzle, and your thesis will have troubles getting off the ground. But if your case is similar, although there were good reasons to believe it would not be, you have a puzzle. Similarly, if your case is deviant, although other cases would have let you assume it to be similar, you have an easy justification for your research: you explain the (unexpected) deviance. In other words, the comparative method is not simply the hobbyhorse of your academic writing instructors: it is a basic methodology for political (or even more generally social) sciences, even when doing a single case analysis. It helps both to achieve more accurate understandings of a case, and a more general understanding of possible patterns across cases. Both would justify your research and the interest in your findings. As a rule of thumb, a single case study would normally prompt the use and comparison of several theories; a critique of a single theory would preferably look at several cases (there are exceptions).

4. The relation between empirics and different types of theorising

There are different ways of theorising. One way consists in distinguishing different modes of theorising. There is meta-theoretical theorising which consists in establishing the underlying epistemological, ontological and methodological assumptions of our social and political theories or in criticising their usage. There is normative theorising whose aim is to clarify the meaning of certain values, as well as the ethical implications of political behaviour or political organisation. It can provide ways to better meet such values. There is constitutive or ontological theorising, which consists in establishing the central meaning of our fundamental concepts: What *is* ‘anarchy’, ‘power’, ‘security’? And there is empirical theorising, which is

where most thesis will find themselves in IR, where research is explicitly geared towards systematically combining theory and empirics.

In the following, I will focus mainly on the latter, yet still showing how the other modes of theorising can be part of this enterprise. This is connected to the two different functions of theories, either providing toolboxes (instrumental) or analytical lenses (constitutive). And it is connected to the different ways in which knowledge speaks beyond itself. We can use empirics for ‘generalisations’, for ‘abstractions’, and for ‘translations’. In all these three ways, knowledge is travelling. But the type of travel is a very different one. Although much of Political Science believes that only (neo-positivist) generalisation is an accepted way to scientifically travel, this is less so in International Relations, where qualitative studies, including of an ethnographic kind have established their importance.

1. Instrumental and constitutive functions of theories

Scholars are interested in theories for two different purposes or cognitive interests that correspond to the dual function of theories. In one case, theories embody ready-made knowledge to be re-used or imitated; they are toolboxes ready to be applied. According to the laws of the market of exchange rates, a country’s central bank that massively buys foreign currency will weaken its own. Since it buys with its own currency, it increases the supply of its currency, which, assuming constant demand, means that its price. i.e. the exchange rate, decreases. Theories provide the background within which to create instruments for practical intervention.

Often less clear is a second purpose or cognitive interest of scholars which is not instrumental, but constitutive. Here, we wish to understand the ‘analytical lenses’ and the way they influence the things we select out of the noise of history. Data does not speak for itself; indeed, it is not even visible as data in the first place. Theories constitute different conceptual lenses with which we identify things in the first place. We do not passively register the world; we actively look for matches for our pre-conceptions. Without such pre-conceptions, no analysis would be possible (which does not imply that they are stable or impervious to learning). That can be also of practical importance, since, in some cases, such conceptions do not only represent but intervene in social reality; they are ‘performative’. For instance, categories when applied to people tend to interact with the self-understanding of people who may end up recognising themselves in those categories (of being ‘not normal’, for instance, because of a certain colour or behaviour).

The interest in the constitutive function of theories informs theoretical theses like in the meta-theoretical and constitutive theorising mentioned above. Being theoretical in their aim does not mean they use no empirics (although they can). Those theses, too, will use empirical findings by others to re-draw or discard the assumptions of existing theories. Should a theory find it systematically difficult to account for certain cases, this result needs to be ‘theorised’: what makes the theory so unsuccessful? You may wish to find out how one can re-define it to achieve a better fit. But you may also look around about other theoretical findings (again related to empirics) that could explain its bad fit.

For instance, realist theories assume actors to be rational value maximisers, where the value is usually expressed as power or security. At times, however, you find empirical cases where states do not act ‘rationally’ by disregarding effects on material security. A rationalist

theory of action would then look for secondary factors which account for this ‘irrationality’. But perhaps states do not only look for material security. Just as with human beings, they may be driven by self-esteem or honour. During World War II, when the authoritarian Greek Prime Minister Metaxas refused the Italian ultimatum, he was sure to lose the battle (although he almost did not). Greece was to sacrifice many lives so as to lose in honour. Inversely, although it seems self-evident that a country’s sense of security is enhanced by being rid of its main enemy, it may not be. One of Gorbachev’s advisers is said to have warned his US counterparts, that, with the end of the Cold War, the USSR did something threatening to the US: ‘we take your enemy away’. In other words, getting rid of the enemy sometimes increases security, but sometimes not, since it destabilises an identity in need or quest of an enemy. In both cases, the analysis is re-framed since action is no longer assumed to be merely driven by value maximisation, but by self-esteem and processes of social recognition. Here, the empirics feed into the check of theoretical assumptions and ultimately into the re-formulation or undermining of theories.

To sum up: Instrumental and constitutive functions of theories will inform different research designs, since once theories are the *product* of knowledge (e.g. empirical generalisations), and once they are the *condition for the very possibility* of knowledge. Theoretical developments are possible in both, they can speak to each other, but they are of a profoundly different manner.

2. Types of empirical theorising (I): Empirical regularities and ‘generalisation’

The relation between the empirical findings and the theories can be multiple. In the classical positivist setup, it works in two ways. First, you may wish to test a theory. This is a deductive procedure. Here, the theory comes first, and by looking at its assumptions, you derive/deduct specific hypotheses for your case(s). These are the outcomes expected if the theory were to prove correct. In this context, it is important to have a specific justification for your case selection. For instance, the case is an easy case, where the theory is supposed to apply, since the conditions are most favourable. That would be a most-likely case design and works well if you can show the theory to provide hypotheses that do *not* fit your case. Inversely, you can choose a case where the theory is supposedly weak, since its scope conditions do not apply well. Here, if you find that it works nevertheless, you can make a point. That would be a least-likely case design. Finding out that a case does not fit where we would expect it not to fit, or fits where it looks evident, is not particularly helpful. Obviously, this design can be applied to more than one case.

Second, you may wish to establish some hypotheses in the first place. This is a more inductive enterprise in that you make causal inferences. In the positivist tradition, theories are empirical generalisations. Positivism assumes the world to be made up of regularities that science uncovers. You have a hunch that there is something regular or systematic in the relation between one factor (variable) and another. You run a relevant quantitative analysis to find out whether some factors are systematically connected. These regularities are the empirical generalisation that the positivist tradition identifies as theories. They can be further tested to specify their scope conditions or, if they do not fit, for being discarded. In other words, the two strategies feed into each other.

3. Types of empirical theorising (II): Ideal-typical or conceptual ‘abstraction’

Our view of the world is made possible by the concepts with which we look at it. The empirical world does not speak directly to us. But sometimes they are not there, or they do not seem to be fitting, and we become aware of this (which is not necessarily so). We need to re-conceptualise. How best to understand ‘the state’ in times of globalisation, ‘the border’, ‘power’, ‘security’, ‘the nation’, and so on? Or at a lower level of abstraction: how best to understand the nature of a country’s foreign policy? What is typical about it? What constitutes / defines it? Here, the empirics feed into the development of ideal types, which are heuristic devices with which to make sense of the world. When Max Weber defined the state through its monopoly of the legitimate use of force, he provides an abstraction that makes sense within his more general understanding of politics (as struggle). This abstraction works by isolating the defining moment of a phenomenon. One does not theorise by establishing a regularity between factors, but by defining the constitutive components of a phenomenon. This phenomenon is both part of theories and something that needs to be theorised itself. And such conceptualisation returns to the drawing board time and again in its contact with empirical analysis. To stay with the example: just think about the different types of states that the Weberian ideal type has generated by looking at the different processes via which legitimate order is achieved in other parts of the world.

This leads to another important difference between generalisations and abstractions. Whereas generalisations try to find regularities, hence similarities, ideal types are there as reference points to establish significant differences, say, how a neo-patrimonial state may differ from a welfare state in its legitimacy processes, or how, within the world of welfare states, there are differences according to the logic this welfare is provided.

4. Types of empirical theorising (III): Recontextualization / ‘translation’

Weber’s conceptualisation of the modern state did ‘travel’ by being applied to all parts of the world. In this case, scholars take the understanding of a phenomenon from one context in which it was developed and put into a different context. They translate the phenomenon from one (empirical, historical) context to another.

Such translation has several features. It is an unavoidable feature of us gaining knowledge: we use knowledge we have to access that knowledge we don’t. We cannot do otherwise. Now, we may be interested in finding similarities across contexts for establishing regularities and generalisation. But we may also be interested in what is ‘lost in translation’, i.e. in the difference the context makes to the understanding of the phenomenon at hand. A second important feature to keep in mind is that translation is a two-way street. When Weber’s concept of the modern state, obviously derived from the mainly European experience, is moved into different contexts, the meaning of its constitutive parts (violence, legitimacy, monopoly) may have to be adapted. In return, such adaptation makes one re-think the way the ideal type has to be understood in its original context. Any translation over space or time is a ‘fusion of horizons’ (Gadamer) in which we learn to move into another context/meaning world, while that move will affect our own.

Research designs in this context are case-oriented, not variable-oriented, i.e. qualitative and often also interpretivist. For the sake of illustration, let me use one type which is ‘case study and theory development’, i.e. where the aim is also clearly theoretical, and one type

which is more ethnographic, i.e. where the aim is empirical, but which nevertheless takes its significance from the way it resonates with significant wider, often called: ‘philosophical’ issues (like: power, violence).

Case study and theory development

In these research designs, case studies are not meant to test hypotheses; they generate hypotheses. And they do not generate hypotheses in terms of regularities. Whereas quantitative approaches see cases as representative of a to-be-defined universe of cases that therefore need to be carefully chosen for their representativity, qualitative approaches may look exactly at those cases where we would think to find a best fit (‘paradigmatic cases’), since the aim is to develop an abstraction that can travel.

One classic way to go about this are typologies. When Gøsta Esping-Andersen developed his famous typology of welfare capitalist regimes, he started from an underlying abstract idea, namely that welfare states are ultimately constituted by an attempt to ‘de-commodify’, i.e. take fundamental parts of the social order, like health, education, access to justice, parts of the labour market (unemployment), etc. outside the market or commercial/profit nexus. On the basis of this underlying theorisation, he developed a typology of three different logics to deal with de-commodification, a liberal residual welfare state, a continental insurance-based welfare state and a universal welfare state. Obviously, once established, such typology is applied to many cases and such re-contextualisation leads to further specifications or indeed critique.

Another way is more process-oriented. Case-centered comparativists are often concerned with processes where the same outcome could be reached by different paths (equifinality) or the same causes or initial events can lead to multiple outcomes (multifinality). For this reason, that process needs to be analysed and cannot just be left as a ‘black box’. In the positivist tradition, a causal mechanism is that which explains the regularity of the relation between two factors (variables). In the more interpretivist tradition, a causal mechanism is a process-factor that may not be triggered, or, if triggered, may have multiple effects. It has some determinacy, but its functioning and/or outcome is contingent. Yet, it has a certain in-built logic, like the classical mechanisms of a self-fulfilling prophecy. In IR, an analysis which is interested in the playing out of one mechanism in different contexts is ‘securitisation’. Its main idea is that political discourse in the West has historically developed in such a manner that successfully labelling an issue one of security allows the usage of extraordinary measures and lifts the issue out of usual political processes. Given different political contexts, the conditions under which this may happen and the effects can be very different. The aim is not to have a general causal mechanism, a regularity then to be double-checked, but to have one mechanism via which to better understand the differences between contexts and processes.

In other words, we use empirics both to establish the logics of such mechanisms and to see the multiplicity of its effects. And the purpose is to make it travel to new cases where we can learn something about the new context through the mechanism and, inversely, can use this new context to rethink the constitutive parts of the mechanism and the felicity conditions for it to work.

Ethnographic / Field research

There are obviously many different research designs in more ethnographic studies. The purpose here is simply to note that ethnographic research always also speaks beyond its field.

Knowledge of something is never only knowledge about it, since we need categories to make sense of the world. Those categories are not universal in the strong sense of equally applicable everywhere, but they can speak to wider audiences and experiences. Hence, ethnographic work is translation par excellence, only that it does locate the site of translation in the field itself. As a result, ethnographic studies usually hook the significance of the field in a theme of wider importance. For instance, quite a number of more ethnographically oriented research in IR and development studies is interested in diffuse processes of domination, therefore often referring to Foucault. Again, they are not ‘applying’ Foucault’s concept of domination, whatever that may mean. But they use it like a channel for their translation that will, as mentioned above, always be a two-way street.

5. General examples of puzzles/contributions

To recapitulate. There are different types of theorising. There is *normative* theorising in a strict sense, i.e. about the ethics of IR. Here, we try to assess or discuss (the conflict of) values in themselves or, when more empirically oriented, the effect of certain political developments on the normative order. There is *meta-theorising* which is mainly geared towards ontological and epistemological assumptions and their relation to explanations. Then, there is *ontological/constitutive* theorising, sometimes also called political theory in a strict sense, which is about the ‘nature of’ the conceptual building blocks of the theories we use (what *is* sovereignty, order, power, security, solidarity, cooperation, war, etc.). Finally, there is *empirical* (or: *explanatory*) theorising which is either driven by empirical generalisations, or case, event or process-centered abstractions, like ideal types, or, finally, by re-contextualising translations. Accordingly, puzzles and the methodology to handle them can be very varied. Some non-exhaustive examples.

I spend more time developing the different theoretical options, since they are usually less known. It is not meant to say that everyone needs to become a theorist, rather, it tends to show that many have more theory in their analysis, as they may be aware of (even if the aim of the thesis is empirical).

1. Theoretical puzzles / designs

Normative theorising

- You propose a normative stance for theorising IR:

E.g.

Levine, Daniel (2012) *Recovering International Relations: The Promise of Sustainable Critique*, Oxford: Oxford University Press (his revised PhD).

Note that very often the difference between the empirical and normative is blurred, since some theorisations connect the two:

Jabri, Vivienne (2012) *The Postcolonial Subject: Claiming Politics/Governing Others in Late Modernity*, Abingdon: Routledge.

Meta-theorising

- You argue that an underlying ontological or epistemological (usually they are combined) phenomenon has not been sufficiently addressed, and if done, yields relevant implications for studying IR.

E.g.

Kurki, Milja (2008) *Causation in International Relations: Reclaiming Causal Analysis*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press (her revised PhD thesis).

- You assess a theory or theorists according to their meta-theoretical assumptions, usually to figure out tensions and contradictions; or, you use meta-theory to fix them.

E.g.

Zehfuss, Maja (2002) *Constructivism in International Relations: The Politics of Reality*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press (her revised PhD thesis).

Constitutive theorising

- You make a conceptual analysis of a central core concept (justifying why this is worthwhile), such as sovereignty, security, power, etc., in general

E.g.

Haas, Ernst B. (1953) 'The Balance of Power: Prescription, Concept or Propaganda?', *World Politics* V, 53 (July): 442-77.

Bartelson, Jens (1995) *A Genealogy of Sovereignty*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press (his revised PhD thesis).

... or applied to a particular theory:

Tucker, Robert W. (1952) 'Professor Morgenthau's Theory of "Realism"', *American Political Science Review* XLVI: 214-224. [on the 'national interest']

- you argue that a particular phenomenon has been so far misunderstood or has been under-theorised (in terms of: under-conceptualised)

Crawford, Neta C. (2000) 'The Passion of World Politics: Propositions on Emotion and Emotional Relationships', *International Security* 24, 4, pp. 116-156. [NB: here the analysis is also trying to specify how this phenomenon may be an explanatory factor]

Bull, Hedley (1977) *The Anarchical Society: A Study of Order in World Politics*, London: Macmillan [NB: here the analysis is about what may constitute the phenomenon.]

Bially Mattern, Janice (2005) *Ordering International Politics: Identity, Crisis, and Representational Force*, London, New York: Routledge (her revised PhD thesis). [NB: here it is the role of identity in constructivist/post-structuralist explanatory theory that is re-conceptualised both theoretically and through her empirical analysis of the Suez Crisis]

Note the role of typologies in this regard:

E.g.

Esping-Andersen, Gøsta (1990) *The Three Worlds of Welfare Capitalism*. Cambridge: Polity Press.

Empirical theorising

- 'Paradigm-comparison': You compare theories with regard to their understanding or explanation of a particular empirical event and show their respective strengths and weaknesses. You might also want to show that the better score for one theory is pure

coincidence or of a more general type (for this you need to compare with other similar events or similar explanations).

E.g.

Lebow, Richard Ned and Thomas Risse-Kappen (eds) (1995) *International Relations Theory and the End of the Cold War*. New York: Columbia University Press.

- 'Hypothesis-testing'

E.g.

Schroeder, Paul W. (1994) 'Historical reality vs. neo-realist theory', *International Security* 19, 1: 108-148. [thesis: the heyday of realist diplomacy does not fit neorealist theory]

Grieco, Joseph M. (1995) 'The Maastricht Treaty, economic and monetary union and the neorealist research programme', *Review of International Studies* 21, 1: 21-40. [thesis: if neorealism can get the model case of the liberals right, then it stays vindicated. Result: It does, but needs some adjustment. Hence, it becomes case study for theory development.]

- You want to show that a particular event or phenomenon looks significantly (why?) different if understood through one theory rather than another. Your thesis is either the unexpected difference, or about the implications if another interpretation be chosen.

E.g.

Morozov, Viatcheslav (2015) *Russia's postcolonial identity: A subaltern Empire in a Eurocentric world*, Houndmills: Palgrave Macmillan.

Allison, Graham T. (1971) *Essence of Decision: Explaining the Cuban Missile Crisis*. Boston: Little Brown. [see also 2nd revised ed. NB: the book is also an exercise in constitutive theorising to the extent that it proposes a new framework of analysis]

- the insufficient understanding (or even the non-existing conception) of a type of events which asks for a comparative analysis emphasising their underlying logic [see also: typologies]

E.g.

Katzenstein, Peter J. (1985) *Small States in World Markets: Industrial Policy in Europe*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press.

- 'Case study and theory development': You use a paradigmatic case or a comparison of cases to develop new components of a theory (besides making also an empirical point)

E.g.

Klotz, Audie (1995) *Norms in International Relations: The Struggle against Apartheid*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press. [Note that it has also a classical type of empirical puzzle: unexpected or sudden policy change of the US towards SA - why?]

Guzzini, Stefano, ed. (2012) *The return of geopolitics in Europe? Social mechanisms and foreign policy identity crises*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. [Social mechanisms reconceptualised for micro-dynamics of a constructivist foreign policy theory]

- all positivist research design that establish a new correlation between variables (descriptive part) and then discuss different mechanisms that lead from the independent to the dependent variable (explanatory part)

2. Empirical puzzles/contributions

- understanding a case or event which is generally misunderstood within the addressed audience:

a) by providing a new logic, argument, interpretation of the existing record, by e.g. connecting formerly unconnected events or causes for their explanation.

E.g.

MccGwire, Michael (1991) *Perestroika and Soviet National Security*. Washington D. C.: The Brookings Institution. [arguing that Perestroika happened despite of the Reagan policies, not because of them]

b) by providing formerly unknown evidence which leads to a new interpretation of events: the classical (pure) historical thesis

6. Drafting a research design: Checklist for starting the journey (what/why/how)

1. Define and justify the precise problematique you would like to explain or understand about this event or theme. (Note: this should involve some literature review of the event / theme that helps you to situate the precise problematique). Specify the body of knowledge – empirical, theoretical or both – *to* which your analysis will contribute. Specify the aim of the analysis, such as, among others: hypothesis testing, theory comparison, theory development, empirical assessment.

2. Formulate a precise question to be answered / a proposition to be explored (theory development) / an ideal type to be established / a hypothesis to be tested / a claim to be defended / a puzzle to be solved / a paradox or dilemma to be addressed (for political theory in particular). More general questions, propositions or hypotheses can be subdivided in a series of more precise ones (Note: this includes the definition of your central research terms and / or variables)

3. Specify and justify the body of knowledge (usually: theories) *with* which you conduct your analysis. This body of knowledge that you use to address your problematique may be a different one from the one which defines your problematique (say: Allison's *Essence of Decision* addresses crisis management but uses psychological theories).

4. Discuss the appropriate means of the analysis or methodology, such as concept analysis, variable-centered comparison, case-centered comparison (or single case), statistics, experimental design, ethnographic methods, or others. (NB. The methods are to be defined in their appropriateness to answer the question / resolve the puzzle /generate or test hypothesis / defend the claim. In other words, the analysis should usually be problem-driven, not method-driven.)

5. Sketch the logic and steps of the actual analysis